

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe

Towards Sustainable Development

D4.1 Launch of Project Website

Project Acronym	PRODIGEES
Project Title	<i>Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development</i>
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PRODIGEES Project Website

The state-of-the-art PRODIGEES website, set up by DIE with support from its Communication Department, is the centre hub of the PRODIGEES Dissemination and Communication Strategy. From the beginning of secondments, it announces, promotes and documents project activities and the benefits or research results beyond the project's own community. It is meant to be attractive for regular visits due to target-group specific sections, frequent updates, neat interconnection to the institution's existing website environment and facilitated by external triggers from local and social media, and the Newsletter. In a special section, it documents PRODIGEES' appearance in media and networks.

The website with the Online Repository of Digital Knowledge Products connects PRODIGEES to the wider public and imparts knowledge needed to integrate sustainability thinking and the interdependencies between Europe and other world regions into life in the digital era. An expected impact is the raised awareness about responsibility and implications of own actions, for instance with a view to energy consumption, online behaviour, or the digital footprint. Visits of the website, clicks on videos/podcasts, re-tweets of infographics and learning content via social media can document the success of the outreach to the wider public.

*Update, December 2020

The second version of the PRODIGEES website provides a considerable formatting and content upgrade. URL: <http://www.prodigees.info>

The PRODIGEES website utilises a long-form format in which the user needs only to scroll in order to encounter content. The content is categorized in headings, such as “News, Publications and Events”, “The PRODIGEES Consortium”, “DIE’s PRODIGEES Team and Contact Information” and “Links for Researchers / Zenodo”. Each section of the long-form can be accessed via a ‘burger menu’ button, which shows a dropdown list of the section titles. Selecting a section title moves the user instantly to the requested part of the long-form.

Rather than hosting content directly on DIE servers, the website embeds PRODIGEES content which is saved in external locations (i.e. the requisite publisher, YouTube, Zenodo, etc.). Therefore, the website becomes a gateway to the project’s content, rather than being itself a repository for data deposit and extraction.

Website Splash Screen (07 December 2020)

March 2020

The first version of the PRODIGEES website URL is:

<https://www.die-gdi.de/en/research/description/details/promoting-research-on-digitalisation-in-emerging-powers-and-europe-towards-sustainable-development-prodigees-1/>.

After its initial setup in March 2020, the webpage will be updated in regular intervals, usually on at least a monthly basis. The updates will reflect the expansion of project activities in the course of the implementation of planned deliverables.

For better accessibility, the PRODIGEES website is planned to be made available with the next update at the following, shortened URL: <https://www.die-gdi.de/prodigees/>.

Screenshot (31 March 2020) of the first version of the webpage:

PRODIGEES
Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik / German Development Institute

RESEARCH POLICY ADVICE TRAINING TEAM LIBRARY PUBLICATIONS EVENTS PRESS ABOUT US

PROMOTING RESEARCH ON DIGITALISATION IN EMERGING POWERS AND EUROPE TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (PRODIGEES)

PRODIGEES is a transnational knowledge cooperation network, aimed at creating a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the impact of digitalisation across the social, economic and environmental dimension of sustainable development and its governance. Funded by the EU's Horizon2020 programme, it analyses conditions under which positive effects of digitalisation can be realised, while at the same time [mitigating] potential negative effects. The project (2020-2023) engages in staff exchange, transnational training and multi-stakeholder dialogue, and establishes a long-term platform of research institutions in the EU and from the MGG network in Brazil, India, Indonesia, Mexico and South Africa.

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Financing:
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Time frame:
2020 - 2023 / ongoing

Co-operation Partner:
Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI); Universität Hamburg (UHAM); Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS); Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV); Instituto Mora (MORA); Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS); Stellenbosch University (SU)

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PROJECT COORDINATION

CO-OPERATION PARTNER

This project is co-funded by the European Union

CURRENT PUBLICATIONS

Socially responsible public procurement (SRPP) in multi-level regulatory frameworks: assessment report on policy space for SRPP regulation and implementation in Germany and Kenya

Stoffel, Tim
Discussion Paper 9/2020

Beyond national climate action: the impact of region, city, and business commitments on global greenhouse gas emissions

Kuramochi, Takeshi / Mark Roelfsema / Angel Hsu / Swithin Lui / Amy Weinfurter / Sander Chan / Thomas Hale / Andrew Clapper / Andres Chang / Niklas Höhne
Externe Publikationen of 30 March 2020

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